

kg K/ha. After deducting the N supplied through NK granules, prilled urea was broadcast at 75 kg N/ha in WS and 100 kg N/ha in DS. P as superphosphate was applied at 37.5 kg/ha in WS and 50 kg/ha in DS. Irrigation water was good quality (EC 0.15 dS/m) and did not contribute any appreciable K. Rice cultivars were IR50 in WS and Co 43 in DS.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications (see table for treatment details). In WS, nutrient uptake and grain yield were similar across treatments, but higher than no K. During DS, nutrient uptake was higher

Effect of topdressing NK granules on nutrient uptake and yield of rice. ^a Coimbatore, India, 1983-84.

Treatment	Wet Season			Dry season		
	N uptake (kg/ha)	K uptake (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	N uptake (kg/ha)	K uptake (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)
No K	91 b	147 b	4.2 b	101 d	158 d	4.6 b
Muriate of potash, all basal	112 a	186 a	5.9 a	115 a	204 a	5.0 a
NK granules - basal	100 a	169 a	5.0 a	106 c	170 c	4.8 b
NK granules at tillering	107 a	178 a	5.1 a	112 ab	177 b	5.1 a
NK granules at tillering + panicle initiation	118 a	170 a	5.8 a	109 bc	181 b	5.0 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

with basal application of muriate of potash, and grain yield equaled that with NK granules topdressed at tillering and at tillering + panicle initiation. □

Influence of rate and time of N application on growth and yield of rice in Pakistan

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We studied the effect of different N levels and timing of prilled urea application on rice in a Typic Camborthids soil (sandy clay loam texture, pH 7.8, EC, 1.22 dS/m, CEC 9.2 cmol/kg, 0.038% N, 10.2 ppm available P, 140.2 ppm K, and 3.4 ppm Zn).

Single basal and equal split N application at 30, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha were compared in a split-plot design with three replications. Plot size was 30 m². All treatments received 28 kg P/ha as single superphosphate. Basal N was broadcast and incorporated in dry soil before transplanting Basmati 370.

Tillers/hill and straw yield increased with each increment of N

Effect of time^a and N level on growth and yield of rice. Faisalabad, Pakistan.

N level (kg/ha)	Tillers (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)	N recovery (%)	N-use efficiency (kg rice/kg N)
		Grain	Straw			
<i>N applied BT</i>						
0	8.1 f	2.6 i	4.4 i	32.2 i	—	—
30	12.7 c	3.2 f	4.7 h	47.8 g	52.0	18.8
60	13.3 bc	3.5 d	6.0 f	59.4 f	45.3	14.8
90	13.2 bc	3.7 b	7.1 d	80.2 d	53.3	12.0
120	13.6 b	3.6 c	7.8 c	82.8 c	42.2	8.4
150	16.4 a	3.5 d	9.1 a	95.9 b	42.5	6.4
<i>N applied 1/2 BT + 1/2 at PI</i>						
0	9.2 e	2.7 h	4.0 j	30.9 j	—	—
30	11.7 d	2.9 g	4.4 i	37.0 h	20.3	6.7
60	12.5 c	3.3 e	5.2 g	47.5 f	27.7	9.5
90	13.0 bc	3.3 e	6.4 e	58.7 f	30.9	6.4
120	13.5 b	3.6 c	6.4 e	73.9 e	35.8	7.5
150	16.6 a	3.9 a	8.3 b	99.9 a	46.0	7.9

^aBT = before rice transplanting in dry soil, PI = at panicle initiation stage before flooding. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

fertilizer, and were higher with single N application (see table). Grain yield was reduced above 90 kg N/ha with all N applied as basal. Yields with split application were not reduced up to 150 kg N/ha. At lower N rates, split application resulted in relatively lower

grain and straw yields. In general, N recovery and agronomic efficiency were lower with higher N rates applied once because of the yield decrease. With split placement of N fertilizer, the rate of yield increase was linear. □

Effect of humic acid on wet season rice

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Humic acids—the complex organic molecules formed by the breakdown and neo-synthesis of organic matter—as liquid salts may help maintain adequate amounts of organic matter in ricefields. We evaluated Energiser 12 PCT (a liquid formulation of alkaline [KOH]

extraction containing 12% humic acid) on growth and yield of rice during 1988 wet season.

Soil was gangetic alluvial (Entisol), sandy loam in texture, with 0.6% organic C, 0.04% total N, 9.3 mg available (Olsen) P/kg, 50 mg available